

FIGURATIVE EXPRESSION OF THE AUTHOR'S LANGUAGE IN ISAJAN SULTAN'S STORIES (EXAMPLE OF KISMAT'S STORY)

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ANNOTATION: The article contains thoughts aimed at revealing the figurative features of the author's language in the stories of Isajon Sultan. Also, in the story of Kismat, the legality of each personalization of the speech and the problem of the artistic work in relation to the situation are brought to light. At the same time, the main ideas of the image style, such as the attitude of the old woman to the little boy, the big boy, and the middle boys, are represented by a large number of characters. Isajon Sultan used images such as the image of a dream or the image of a family with many children, butterfly, fish, typical of the works of many authors of world literature.

KEY WORDS: Dream image, problematics of an artistic work, figurative image, expression of the author's language with characters, artistic analysis.

In the story, the image of a blind old woman living with her children reveals the author's attitude towards social characters with an ideological content. After the younger son's dream about the goldfish and his dreams reached the middle son, the middle son reached out to the older son, and the older son eagerly fried it. The style of the image is shown in an unusual integrity. Taking away or destroying something that is the essence of a person's life puts them in a very difficult situation. And the younger son experiences such events. The middle son's conflict with his father's personality imposes an additional conflict on the main character, i.e. the author's language is figurative because of the scenes of his father getting drunk, raising his hand against his mother, and fearing his father. It can be seen that it is expressed in a way. A few years after her father's death, the feeling of hatred that remains in her heart is also expressed in the speech of the old woman. According to the style of Isajon Sultan, the forms of attitude given by the language of each character reveal Isajon Sultan's skill in artistic creation. The average boy's fantasy about the mysterious fish and his image must have been the direct motivation for the development of events. In the implementation of the ideological content, the expression of dream images and fish images is often found in Uzbek literature. Especially with the advent of dream imagery in folk epics, stories, and novels, the event changes the attitude towards the event. This work is not far from such symbolism. This is also one of the artistic elements that can be used to increase the author's rights to increase the value of the work. "Spirituality is not a concept that appeared yesterday or today, it is a great value that has been living and developing together with our people for centuries. From the day he was born, until the last moment of his life, a person grows up and matures within the values and traditions of the people he belongs to. Even a person who considers himself a stranger to folklore, who is completely far from the definition of this term, has been formed under the influence of these ancient traditions. Genres of folk creativity, which are the spiritual wealth of our nation, and its immortal heroes, the experience of artistic creativity serve as the main

spiritual and artistic source for the creation and development of written literature. In fact, there is probably not a single word artist who did not enjoy the oral creativity of the people and was not nourished by its spiritual wealth. In the same way, when we read the stories of Isajon Sultan, we see that he effectively used examples of folk oral creativity.[1]

The reason for the division of the story into structural sequences is revealed by the implementation of a specific task assigned to each creator, each hero, character. Isajon Sultan, in particular, aims to reveal such a psychological image in his works, or a direct connection with nature in the style of images: crackling firewood or images of nature, images of hot cancer are examples of these words. We can see that the child's sudden development of hate feelings is a sequential and step-by-step change in attitude towards the past. In this regard, the problematic of the artistic work is realized, the problematic of the artistic work, that is, the person or event that caused the problem is caused by the wounds of the father's death, which are left to this day. In this regard, the author expresses several directions regarding the father's personality. The opinion of an average son differs from that of a younger son, because the older son's attitude towards his father, especially in the student's personality, creates different opposition. "Do you remember the ones that I clung to your hand, do you remember?.. Here is a burning fire for you".[2] The father appeared to the old woman in a dream, the father came as a fish, and the father came as a fish, together with the belief that the mother would recover after eating that fish, the thoughts and feelings of the people of that time. It is also evident in revealing the relationship. The image of the open fields or the sentences in the dialogue causes a breakdown of the sequence in the work. It seems that everything in the play should be completed with the attitude of the old woman. Although the old woman is depicted as a mother who does not tire of telling stories that will set an example for her children, she becomes silent after the issue of the goldfish.

In the work of Isajon Sultan, the emergence of the problem of artistic image and artistic work occurs in every detail. The ghosts of the little boy are proportional to the image style and its character given by the author's speech. That he is young reveals the love of our simple Uzbek people and our childish people towards the golden fish. The dream image is related to the solution of the events presented in the dream. Also, the concept of trust in finding a solution with a fish reveals the simple and very trust of our Uzbek people. In this regard, the style found in world literature motivates the existing modes of expression to work in sequence. The literary details that increase the artistic value of this trick are as follows:

- dream image. As in many literary and artistic works, this story of Isajon Sultan depicts a dream;

- representation of the solution with external objects. This process gives a solution to all the events that happened to the father's personality with a single fish, and feelings of trust are created;

- due to the large number of characters. Each hero or character in Asrar has a separate life and has a unique destiny and character. This causes the work to become popular. The reason for this is that the presence of various heroes and characters creates interest in the work in the reader. "Motive (in psychology) is a factor that causes the fulfillment of a certain goal in human activity, and a motive is an internal impulse that urges a person to action and activity, appearing as a high form of need. It includes need and instinct, inclination and emotion, ideal and other motives. In modern psychology, the term motive is used to describe various events and situations that activate the subject. Motive arises and forms on the basis of

need. Sometimes the concept of "motive" is replaced by the terms "emotion", "goal", "setting". Sometimes it is characterized by the concepts of impulse, instigator, exclamation.

"Know that you can't talk back to your father, you can't pass him when he's walking, you can't pass food before him, you can't stand in front of him with your hands folded and your neck bowed must not speak with a loud voice! The word of the father is the law, there is a special way of making words for him... That is why they said that the father is pleased, God is pleased, does this not argue about the greatness of the father's breed?

Oh, the candle of my eyes and the light of my eyes,

There will be no time without human faith

Don't be an enemy of God,

If your head reaches the sky, don't do it." [3]

Istajon Sultan's art is similar to that of many artists in the world. The reason for this is that the artistic effectiveness of the work increases by dividing the events into parts or expressing the attitudes of several characters to the same event. Through this, the appearance of dialogues, monologues in the author's language is also related to details. Isajon Sultan is a rarely touched subject in world literature. The creation of stories of this type is important for the formation of the attitude towards each personal speech or for revealing the problematic of the artistic work in the intellectual research. Each character has their own way of thinking about the personality of the father. The fact that the author has a social character reveals the image of the society, and the visual representation of the things happening in the society is visible in the speech of each character. It is this situation that leads to the violation of the readability of the work of art and the contrast sequence.

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